

One-step synthesis of carbon-sulphur heterocyclic ring by electrochemical reduction of carbon disulphide at platinum electrode

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Abstract : The electro reductive cyclization of carbon disulphide in nonaqueous solvent is reported here. At constant potential, the electrolysis of carbon disulphide was carried out in the presence of an electrophile i.e. alkyl cation, acyl cation etc. using *N,N*-dimethylformamide, acetonitrile or DMSO as a nonaqueous solvent and tetrabutylammonium iodide, tetraethylammonium phosphate as a supporting electrolyte. Electro reductive cyclization of carbon disulphide gives 4,5-disubstituted thio-1,3-dithiole-2-thione at platinum cathode. This is a one pot electrochemical synthesis which takes place at room temperature.

Keywords : Carbon disulphide, electrochemical reduction, platinum electrode, synthesis.

Introduction

Electrochemistry can be considered a green methodology in organic synthesis due to its non-polluting reagent, the electron¹. At constant potential, a variety of electrochemical reactions takes place when a solution containing a reacting material is oxidized or reduced which depend on the structure of reacting molecules and the environment viz. nature of solvent, value of electrode potential and supporting electrolytes²⁻⁴. One or other electrochemical processes can be made favorable by adjusting experimental parameters⁵. Direct electrochemical oxidations or reductions of substrates utilize practically mass-free electrons as the only reagent⁶. In this communication, we are reporting the result of our studies on electrolysis of carbon disulphide at constant potential in nonaqueous solvent. The electrochemical reduction of carbon disulphide in aprotic media provides synthetic entry into multisulphur species based on the 1,3-dithiole ring structure. This carbon-sulphur heterocyclic ring can be prepared either by reduction of carbon disulphide with active metals⁷ or electrochemical reduction method as described by us. The electrolysis of carbon disulphide under the special parameters, afford the formation of 4,5-dithio-1,3-dithiole-2-thione dianion **3**, which in the presence of a suitable electrophile gives 4,5-bis-dialkylthio-

1,3-dithiole-2-thiones. These carbon-sulphur heterocyclic rings are of growing interest due to their use in the synthesis of fine chemicals⁸, in agricultural, medicine⁹ and as precursors of heterocycles with biological activity¹⁰.

Results and discussion

Stiemecke *et al.*⁷ investigated that the reduction of carbon disulphide in *N,N*-dimethylformamide by the use of potassium or sodium metal in good yield. Here active metals are used as inert precursors for reduction of carbon disulphide. But in chemical method the use of active metals are hazardous and dangerous in handling. This method cannot be employed for micro level reaction because it is so difficult to measure the active metals in millimole. The second alternative, also based on the activation of inert precursors through electron transfer, consists in pulsing the potential of an electrode alternately to anodic and cathodic potential to generate in turn an electrophile and a nucleophile¹¹. On the way to study electroorganic synthesis (EOS)^{12,13} utilizing platinum electrode, a novel synthetic route from carbon disulphide to heterocyclic ring was invented in our laboratory¹⁴. In order that the highly reactive and thus short-lived species viz. radical anion **1** which we wished to employ should

meet by diffusion and then react, the distance between the sites where they are generated should be as small as possible¹⁵.

Singh and coworkers¹⁶ have studied some cathodic process by using platinum electrode. Electro reductive cyclization of carbon disulphide gives 4,5-disubstituted thio-1,3-dithiole-2-thiones at platinum cathode. Whole electrochemical reaction is represented below (Scheme 1).

be described in a series of steps involving cyclization with electron transfer. In the first step of the reaction, carbon disulphide takes an electron at cathode to afford an anion radical 1, which is highly dependent on the ease of further reduction of it with other molecules of carbon disulphide to next intermediate 2. The intermediate 2 removes sulphide anion to afford a stable intermediate 3 by taking two electrons. The presence of sulphide anion was

where R = -CH₃, -C₂H₅, -COCH₃, -COC₆H₅, -CH₂C₆H₅ and X = -I, -Cl, -OR'

Scheme 1

The formation of heterocyclic ring may be rationalized by a probable mechanism (Scheme 2). During electrolysis the carbon disulphide undergoes reduction in non-aqueous solvent and the mechanism of the reaction can

detected in reaction mixture by chemical test. The solution becomes deep red colour and intermediate 3 also extracted and recrystallised in the form of salts with red crystals. Many efforts have been made to obtain this use-

4a (R = -CH₃), 4b (R = -COCH₃), 4c (R = -COAr) and 4d (R = -CH₂Ar)

Scheme 2

Note

Scheme 3

ful intermediate minimizing the environmental impact, avoiding the use of various solvents, catalysts etc. The anionic active species viz. 4,5-dithio-1,3-dithiole-2-thione dianion 3 generated by cathodic reduction of carbon disulphide may be attacked by electrophiles, for example, alkyl and acyl halides. The alkylation and acylation of this dianion intermediate yields 4,5-disubstituted thio-1,3-dithiole-2-thione as a final product.

The resulting skeleton (4,5-dithio-1,3-dithiole-2-thione dianion 3) have been utilized in the synthesis of crowned tetrathiafulvalene derivatives¹⁷ and organometallic complexes¹⁸⁻²⁰ of Ni, Pt, Ag, Sb and Ho. The S...S contact assembled silver(I) complexes of 4,5-ethylenedithio-1,3-dithiole-2-thione have unique supramolecular networks²¹. In addition the 5-ylidene-4,5-dithio-[4,5-d]-1,3-dithiole-2-thione framework is an important synthetic precursor of multidimensional organic superconductors and conductors²².

The electro reductive cyclization of carbon disulphide gives the corresponding cyclized product (4a-d). This pattern of cyclization is quite different from that caused by a chemical route. At higher potential, the yield of the products may be low (Table 1) because of possible dimerization of dianion intermediate 3 to give a complex mixed

product. Also if the electrolysis of carbon disulphide was carried out at -2.00 V without use of any other reagents, it was observed that the dianion intermediate 3 with one other carbon disulphide gives 1,3,5,7-tetrathiapentalene-2,6-dithione 5. But these negative features can be controlled by controlling the concentration of starting materials, electrode potential and time. Further elucidation of reaction mechanism and its general applications to other carbon skeletons are currently under investigation in our laboratory and will be discussed in due course.

Conclusion :

It is evident from the studies that electrochemical synthesis of 4,5-disubstituted thio-1,3-dithiole-2-thione was carried out with simple nonaqueous solvent and supporting electrolyte at room temperature. The electro organic synthesis is expected to be an important organic synthetic tool in future because of its diverse application in industry in addition to compatibility with green chemistry^{23,24}. The electrochemical synthesis is simple and ecofriendly therefore it is a part of green chemistry.

Experimental

The electrolysis was carried out at constant potential in four necked 50 ml undivided cell. For constant poten-

Table 1. Current-potential data as recorded by potential cum galvanostat

Name of substrates	Potential (V)	Current (A)	Time (h)	Supporting electrolytes	Product	Yield (%)
a b						
CS ₂ Methyl bromide	-1.75	12.6	2	Tetraethylammonium phosphate	4a	69
CS ₂ Methyl bromide	-1.55	14.4	2	Tetrabutylammonium iodide	4a	73
CS ₂ Ethyl acetate	-1.70	17.1	2	Tetrabutylammonium iodide	4b	62
CS ₂ Ethyl acetate	-1.50	13.3	2	Tetraethylammonium borate	4b	58
CS ₂ Acetyl chloride	-1.85	19.4	2	Tetrabutylammonium iodide	4b	61
CS ₂ Benzoyl acetate	-1.75	10.4	2	Tetraethylammonium phosphate	4c	56
CS ₂ Benzyl chloride	-1.45	8.5	2	Tetraethylammonium phosphate	4d	53
CS ₂ Benzyl chloride	-1.60	15.6	2	Tetrabutylammonium iodide	4d	66

tial electrolysis we have used conventional three electrode undivided cell assembly designed in our laboratory using 1 cm × 0.5 cm platinum electrode²⁵ as working as well as counter electrode. The platinum electrodes are surrounded from one side with glass material and saturated-calomel electrode²⁶ (SCE) is used as reference electrode. Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes using Toshniwal's melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Compounds were purified by column chromatography. ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE II-400 (400 MHz FT NMR) spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard; IR (KBr) spectra on Perkin-Elmer 1800 and Shimadzu 8201 PC (4000–350 cm⁻¹) FTIR spectrophotometer; mass spectra on Jeol D-300 (EI) and Jeol SX-102 (FAB) spectrometer.

The reaction mixture contains 50 ml of the solution of 10 ml of carbon disulphide using 40 ml of acetonitrile or DMF as a nonaqueous solvent. DMF is the choice of solvent because it is resistance and unreactive with intermediate anion radical species²⁷. As a supporting electrolyte, we used 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium borate, lithium perchlorate, tetrabutylammonium iodide or tetraethylammonium phosphate separately for each electrolysis. The working electrode potential was maintained between -1.50 and -2.15 V vs SCE. At the initial stage, the reaction mixture was transparent and colourless and as the electrolysis proceeded, the whole reaction mixture gets darkened due to the formation of reddish coloured anionic active species viz. 4,5-dithio-1,3-dithiole-2-thione dianion intermediate. After 5 min of electrolysis, other reactants with calculated amount were mixed in it for alkylation and acylation. As electrolysis proceeded the platinum cathode surface was covered with dark reddish layer of the product which was continuously diffused in the bulk into the solution. For the properly diffusion of product from platinum electrode surface, we used magnetic stirrer. The product obtained after electrolysis was extracted from the solution by simple extraction method using distilled water and chloroform. After extraction the product was recrystallized in acetonitrile, the product obtained was a pink coloured shining crystalline solid.

The product 4,5-disubstituted thio-1,3-dithiole-2-thione was analyzed by chemical as well as spectral method.

4,5-Bis[methylthio]-1,3-dithiole-2-thione (4a) : Yield 73%; m.p. 127–129 °C (Found : C, 26.33; H, 2.81; S,

70.42. Calcd. for C₅H₆S₅ : C, 26.54; H, 2.65; S, 70.78%); IR (KBr) : 2866, 1450, 1408, 1242 (C=S), 1136, 1055, 938, 885, 705, 685 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.25 (s, CH₃); MS (%) m/z : 226, 197.

4,5-Bis[acetylthio]-1,3-dithiole-2-thione (4b) : Yield 68%; m.p. 117–121 °C (Found : C, 29.62; H, 2.01; O, 11.56; S, 56.52. Calcd. for C₇H₆O₂S₅ : C, 29.78; H, 2.12; O, 11.34; S, 56.73%); IR (KBr) : 2825, 1705 (C=O), 1615 (S-CO), 1410, 1214 (C=S), 1122, 1035, 861, 715, 690 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.15 (s, CH₃); MS (%) m/z : 282, 197.

4,5-Bis[benzoylthio]-1,3-dithiole-2-thione (4c) : Yield 56%; m.p. 177–179 °C (Found : C, 51.32; H, 2.58; O, 7.76; S, 38.92. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₀O₂S₅ : C, 50.49; H, 2.46; O, 7.88; S, 39.41%); IR (KBr) : 3015 (Ar-H), 1683 (C=O), 1610 (S-CO), 1565, 1435, 1400, 1244 (C=S), 1124, 1040, 858, 707, 675 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.45–7.51 (m, Ar-H); MS (%) m/z : 406, 197.

4,5-Bis[benzylthio]-1,3-dithiole-2-thione (4d) : Yield 66%; m.p. 157 °C (Found : C, 53.32; H, 3.78; S, 42.92. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₄S₅ : C, 53.95; H, 3.70; S, 42.32%); IR (KBr) : 2815, 1540, 1435, 1400, 1232 (C=S), 1112, 1022, 922, 872, 700, 670 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.85 (s, CH₂) and 7.59–7.65 (m, Ar-H); MS (%) m/z : 378, 197.

1,3,5,7-Tetrathiapentalene-2,6-dithione (5) : Yield 73%; m.p. 203–204 °C (Found : C, 20.09; S, 79.17. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₄S₅ : C, 19.92; S, 80.08%); IR (KBr) : 1062, 953, 892, 769, 670 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); MS (%) m/z : 240, 197.

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